

eDNAAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Report

Roadmap for implementation: Stakeholder Survey Results

Work Package 5

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Executive summary

As part of the ongoing stakeholder consultation process on the proposed recommendations by eDNAqua-Plan to move to a more harmonised and interoperable eDNA digital ecosystem, a survey was conducted by Seascope Belgium to collect feedback on the timeline and feasibility of implementing the proposed recommendations and actions. The data collected with the survey will contribute to the final Technical Blueprint and Roadmap for Implementation. This report presents the results of the survey.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BOCD	British Oceanographic Data Centre
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive from EMBL
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAIRe	FAIR eDNA project
IAB	International Advisory Board
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
LOD	Linked Open Data
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
Syke	Finnish Environment Institute
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee

1. Introduction

eDNAqua-Plan, a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project, assessed the current state of the aquatic environmental DNA (eDNA) (meta)data landscape and came up with technical recommendations and actions to bridge identified gaps in the system and to help shift the digital eDNA ecosystem to a more harmonised and interoperable state. The current and proposed future eDNA digital landscape is presented in ‘eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7: The eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal (Boulanger et al., 2025). The recommendations proposed by eDNAqua-Plan to move to the future landscape have shared with various stakeholders, such as data providers, data processors, repositories, and end-users for their feedback to adapt the recommendations and actions to the community’s needs, to get buy-in and to ensure feasibility of implementation. The final recommendations will be included in the Technical Blueprint and Roadmap for Implementation to ultimately help guide us from a fragmented and difficult to navigate eDNA data ecosystem to a more harmonised system, built on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles. eDNAqua-Plan’s legacy will support future biodiversity monitoring programmes, contribute to realising the potential of eDNA data for multiple applications and support the objectives of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, the EU Green Deal, the Ocean Pact and OceanEye.

A first round of feedback on the recommendations proposed in the eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal was collected during a two day online Blueprint Stakeholder Workshop organised by Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) and WP5 partners (eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 14: Blueprint workshop report, Exter et al., 2026). Building on this, a survey was developed by Seascope Belgium (SSBE) that included the feedback from the workshop. The survey was published from December 19, 2025 to March 6, 2026 using the EUSurvey online survey-management system tool. The questions in the survey focused on the timeline and feasibility of the recommendations and the actors responsible for implementing the recommendations to make the vision a reality. All respondents provided consent regarding privacy and GDPR compliance as outlined in the survey. This document summarises the outcomes of the survey.

Survey Design and Practicalities

The survey contained all the recommendations from the conceptual landscape with a repeated set of questions to solicit feedback on the expected time frame, challenges for implementation and resources necessary. The questions were divided into sections representing the different phases in the eDNA dataflow from sampling to publishing. Within the sections, the questions were addressed to specific stakeholder groups. Each question had the option to provide further feedback. All the questions were optional so participants were free to answer their preferred set of questions based on their own background or current work experience. An estimated completion time was provided for each section to respect participants’ time. It was estimated that the survey could take 10 to 30 minutes depending on how many sections were filled in.

For the recommendations in each of the sections, participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the proposed recommendations using a sliding scale ranging from “fully agree” to “fully disagree.” They were then asked to assess the perceived feasibility of implementing the recommendations, considering various types of potentially limiting resources: technical, policy and strategic, and human resources (time and budget). Finally, participants were asked whether the recommendations were already being implemented within the initiatives they represented.

Communication and Outreach of the survey

The survey was published in December, and widely communicated in early January, after the winter holiday period to increase its visibility. The survey was also shared via email with 151 stakeholders that were identified by the registration form, personal connections, the previous stakeholder engagement workshop and from the eDNAqua-Plan stakeholder mapping activity, which included actors in the eDNAqua-Plan pipeline from sample collection to application, as well as networks and multipliers to further promote its visibility. A communication toolkit was created for partners and contacts who were not directly involved to effectively share the message. There was a weekly post on LinkedIn, BlueSky and X with visuals and engaging quotes. Additionally, there was interaction in Slack’s Environmental

DNA community. Multiple initiatives, groups and organisations were sent the communication toolkit with the request to share with their broader network. The survey was posted on websites (Southern eDNA society and EuroGOOS news) and published in the European Marine Board newsletter. Partners from the consortium were encouraged to reach out to individuals and acquaintances to maximise outreach.

Planned stakeholder engagement events

An expert stakeholder workshop was later organised to build further on the outputs from the earlier WPs, in particular WP3 and WP4, the feedback collected during the Task 5.1 workshop in October, the stakeholder survey, and from International Advisory Board (IAB) members. The workshop targeted stakeholders engaged in biomonitoring, in particular those from the public and private sector who generate/use eDNA data but who may not be data specialists. The main objective was to share the developing recommendations and discuss the application of eDNA-based biomonitoring and related data-sharing challenges and opportunities, to help shape the proposed recommendations to support implementation.

2. Results of the survey

2.1 Geographical scope and respondents representation

In total 23 responses were submitted. The region where most respondents were located was Europe with 17 responses, followed by Australia with 3 responses, and the USA, South-America and Africa each with one response. The geographical scope of the respondents is shown in Figure 1. The actual work/projects/ initiatives that the respondents represented had a broad geographic coverage, with 6 initiatives operating globally, 5 focusing on regions outside of Europe, and the rest being within Europe.

Geographical Scope of Survey Respondents

Figure 1. Geographical scope of the survey's respondents. Colours indicate the countries per continent.

Most respondents identified as data generators and/or publishers, with 16 and 12 responses respectively. All components of the eDNA landscape were represented, with multiple respondents indicating involvement across multiple components. Genetic laboratories were most frequently identified as describing the respondent's work, project, organisation, or initiative (15 responses), followed by DNA data publishers (12), biodiversity data publishers (11), bioinformatics groups and reference libraries (10). Taxonomic systems and backbones were selected by 5 respondents, while biobanks and culture collections were each represented by 3 responses. 1 respondent indicated involvement in other components. Respondents showed involvement across all steps of the eDNA data collection and submission workflow, with relatively similar numbers for sampling, laboratory procedures, bioinformatics, processed sequence data, taxonomic assignment, and eDNA occurrences in biodiversity

databases, between 70% and 87% of the respondents. Taxonomic backbone services and biobank data infrastructure/services were less frequently represented, accounting for 22% and 13% of responses, respectively.

2.2 Feedback on the proposed recommendations based on (dis)agreement, feasibility related to resources, reference libraries and metadata standards

The proposed recommendations were divided into the following survey sections:

General, A) Sampling, B) Laboratory procedures, C) Raw sequence data, D) Bioinformatics analysis, E) Processed sequence data, F) Taxonomic assignment and reference libraries, G) eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases, H) Taxonomic backbone and I) Biobank's data infrastructures/ services.

2.2.1 Agreement and disagreement as indicators for priority

The level of agreement or disagreement per recommendation was determined to try and establish the priority among the recommendations. This was done by assigning all the respondents' scores a weight to reflect their (dis)agreement with respondents having more strong opinions, having more weight in the results. For each question the weighted score was calculated as a mean of all the responses for that question. Positive scores indicate overall agreement, negative scores indicate disagreement, and values near zero showed mixed or neutral opinions. A threshold of 0.3 was used to classify the responses in three groups, namely 'mostly agree' when the weighted score was > 0.3 , 'mostly disagree' when weighted scores were < -0.3 and 'not clear' if it was in between. The results are visualised in Figure 2. The respondents mostly agreed on all posed recommendations except for six, namely:

- Define and keep intermediary files, with FAIR naming conventions (e.g. those included in the FAIRe checklist project) (D.2).
- Improve dataset citation and crediting e.g. by implementing a peer review process for data publications (similar to those of scientific journals) (2).
- Implement integration of sample metadata collected with smartphone apps already used for sample collection (e.g. NMDC Field Notes mobile app, PlutoF GO app) (A.4).
- Enforce the mapping of omics and the traditional taxonomic naming systems to have more discoverable and understandable eDNA results for the biodiversity data user (G.7).
- Publish metadata using RDF, LOD, and web-tech to ensure submissions are findable and accessible (3)
- Make use of Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) to generate required metadata in a standardised way (B.1)

Figure 2. Agreement or disagreement per recommendation. The results are based on their weighted scores and a consensus threshold of 0.3 was applied. The recommendations were divided into the different phases of the eDNA data landscape. Q = question, no letter = General, A = Sampling, B = Laboratory procedures, C = Raw sequence data, D = Bioinformatics analysis, E = Processed sequence data, F = taxonomic assignment and reference libraries, G = eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases, H = Taxonomic backbone, and I = Biobank's data infrastructures/services.

The proposed recommendations with the highest levels of agreement can be grouped into four main topics, namely:

Collaboration and integration

- Better collaboration between various national, global and thematic biodiversity data publishers in adopting common data and metadata standards and schemata (G.2).
- Improve collaboration and mapping of omics and traditional taxonomic naming systems so that eDNA results are more discoverable and understandable by biodiversity data users and that changes can be dealt with efficiently and in a scientific correct way (H.1).
- Improve data integration from national and institutional databases into global databases (E.2).

Funding

- Create long-term funding streams for reference libraries with the proposed EU-level certification and quality label, identifying them as a resource of strategic importance (F.5).

Metadata standards

- Ensure sufficient metadata is provided describing the main processing steps (E.4).
- Recommend, define and implement essential metadata and common taxonomic curation principles, anchored in international methodological and laboratory standards, that enable quality-control and curation (and thus establish the reliability of the taxonomic assignment later on) (F.1).

Training

- Provide training in sampling, in particular related to metadata for fieldwork and experiments and for subsequent processing (4).

2.2.3 Feasibility of the recommendations based on policy/strategy, technical and human resources

To assess whether the proposed recommendations are feasible to implement, three different aspects of implementation were considered, namely from policy/strategy, technical and human resource (time/budget) perspectives. The results are shown in Figure 3. The responses were converted into percentages, ignoring blank fields. It is noticeable that implementation is perceived as most challenging in terms of human resources compared to technical and policy-related resources.

Figure 3. The perceived feasibility for each recommendation per required resource. The resources are of a policy/strategic, technical and human resources nature. Only filled in answers were taken into account, boxes left empty were disregarded. The recommendations were divided into the identified sections of the eDNA data landscape. X = General, A = Sampling, B = Laboratory procedures, C = Raw sequence data, D = Bioinformatics analysis, E = Processed sequence data, F = taxonomic assignment and reference libraries, G = eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases, H = Taxonomic backbone, and I = Biobank's data infrastructures/services.

2.2.4 Taxonomic assignments and reference libraries

Reference library architectures

eDNAqua-Plan's vision aims to maintain independently curated reference libraries, but ensure that they follow common, guiding curation principles and metadata requirements, enabling them to be interconnected and easily discoverable.

This vision relies on three main pillars:

- i) Reference libraries are curated, for sequence quality as well as taxonomic reliability. All primary sequence data are deposited in or harvested from primary nucleotide repositories (ENA, GenBank, BOLD). The quality control and taxonomic curation of these sequences then follows a set of guiding principles, where the goal of the taxonomic curation is to homogenise taxonomic names for a given phylogenetic clade (or for identical/ near-identical sequences).
- ii) All reference libraries adhere to a set of minimal but essential metadata accompanying the reference sequence data. This restricted set of fields allow end-users to easily identify whether the taxonomic assignment linked to a barcode is trustworthy, and be able to filter database entries according to a set of pertinent criteria (geographic location, habitat type, environmental parameters, etc.).
- iii) Reference libraries are connected in a federated system, which relies on common data formats, interoperable metadata fields, and a decentralised data architecture. This data

architecture must ensure a federated network allowing for each reference library to maintain their independence, while still making the data easy to find and query.

13 respondents agreed with this vision focusing on maintaining the independence of individual, curated reference libraries but connecting them in a federated network, 4 replied no and 6 did not answer the question.

Based on this vision, two architectures for a federated system of curated reference libraries were proposed.

- i) Independent reference libraries that are fully decentralised, have common formats, and a common (meta)data search tool or crawler. Reference libraries are individually managed and maintained on separate servers. They ensure that their data is available in an agreed-upon format, following the proposed metadata and data standard, and accessible through an API. A data or metadata search portal or engine would then allow querying the curated reference libraries that adhere to the common format to make their data findable across libraries (Fig 4.).
- ii) Independent reference libraries that are also individually managed and maintained on separate servers, but with periodic data exports in common formats to a centralised repository. Reference libraries are individually managed and maintained on separate servers. Data exports are released in an agreed-upon format, following the proposed metadata and data standard, in a central repository. This central repository centralises the versioned copies of separate databases in one location, and allows easy access from the different sources (Fig 4.).

Figure 4. i) Reference libraries architecture type 1: independent libraries, fully decentralised, common formats, and a common (meta)data search tool or crawler. ii) Reference libraries architecture type 2: independent libraries with periodic data exports in common formats to a centralised repository.

The first architecture type describing independent and decentralised reference libraries with a common search engine was most voted for with 11 answers. The independent reference libraries with regular, centralised data exports received 7 votes. 5 respondents did not answer the question.

Metadata standards

A reference barcode must be accompanied by a minimum set of metadata. The DNA sequence is considered as primary data and all accompanying information as metadata. Having the appropriate metadata accompanying a reference sequence allows verification of the identification of the sequence, which is crucial to curate taxonomic assignments and ensure the quality/ reliability of downstream results.

showed a European and global reach and covered the different areas of the eDNA digital landscape. The respondents' feedback extended to all aspects of the survey, thereby providing valuable insights into the priorities and feasibility of the proposed recommendations. Overall, the recommendations were received positively, with respondents most often indicating agreement or strong agreement. Disagreement originated because the proposed recommendations were complex, open to interpretation, too costly and/or not easy to implement, for example, related to the proposal to implement LIMS systems (B1). In regards to improving the dataset citation and crediting by implementing a peer review process for data publication (2), respondents were concerned that significant human input will be necessary, putting additional pressure on already overstretched scientists and data managers. Concerns were also raised about the handling of sensitive or indigenous data that cannot be made publicly accessible, which might be disadvantageous for scientists working with such datasets that want to publish their work. Respondents were generally concerned that implementing these recommendations would result in more work with less time and little to no reimbursement.

The majority of respondents that answered the questions regarding the reference libraries agreed with eDNAqua-Plan's vision to maintain independently curated reference libraries, but ensure that they follow common, guiding curation principles and metadata requirements. Most preferred an architecture in which reference libraries would function independently and decentralised, but with common formats and a (meta)data search engine or crawler. The main challenges identified to establish a recognition system and connections like this between recognised reference databases are of a technical nature, namely the curation itself and implementation with the existing databases and their established infrastructures. Creating long-term funding streams for reference libraries with proposed EU-level certification and quality label (F.4) was considered to be essential for such a sustainable solution.

Cultural/behavioural change and increased financial resources/ funding will be necessary to accommodate the concerns and support the implementation of the required recommendations. Actors in the pipeline will need (and want) additional training and guidance from the start on how to manage their data. From the results of the survey and previous workshops, we can conclude that there is a willingness in the community to make changes, but it will need strong coordination, and evident and clear steps to provide the necessary capacity building and financial resources to do this.

4. References

- Boulanger, E., Exter, K., Paupério, J., Suominen, S., Provoost, P., Rimet, F., Picazo Mozo, A., Camacho, A., Babo, C., Veríssimo, J., Norros, V., Hablützel, P., Pavloudi, C., Meissner, K., & Woollard, P. (2025). *eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7: The eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal v1*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16090825>
- Exter, K., Boulanger, E., Camacho, A., Collart, T., Hablützel, P., Koole, C. A., McMeel, O., Pavloudi, C., Picazo Mozo, A., Suominen, S., & Woollard, P. (2026). *eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 14: Blueprint workshop report*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18833437>

A. Addendum

Table 1. Survey

eDNAqua-Plan: Stakeholder Consultation Survey

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

eDNAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Introduction

The Horizon Europe funded eDNAqua-Plan project is developing a Technical Blueprint and Roadmap to move from a fragmented and difficult to navigate eDNA data ecosystem to a more harmonised system, guided by FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles. The project has analysed the current eDNA landscape from sampling to publishing and proposed a set of recommendations and targeted actions to achieve an optimised landscape (See “Conceptual Landscape Proposal” in the background documents).

The purpose of this survey is to gather your feedback on these proposed recommendations.

The data collected will be collated into a summary report and contribute to the final eDNAqua-Plan Technical Blueprint and Roadmap.

The survey layout

The eDNA data landscape is complex and this is reflected with distinct sections for the component parts, from sampling to publishing (see page tabs in the toolbar at the top). Each page contains specific recommendations, some of which are targeted towards specific stakeholders. We would encourage you to please take the time and respond where you can, although some sections/questions may not be relevant to you. For this reason, **all questions in the sections are optional. The survey can also be saved and completed in stages.**

The survey takes **between 10 and 30 minutes** to answer, depending on how many sections you complete. This survey will be available online **until 12 February 2025**.

We greatly appreciate your time and support in contributing to this study!

Privacy and GDPR

This survey is conducted by Seascope Belgium, a partner in eDNAqua-Plan, on behalf of the consortium. For further information about eDNAqua-Plan and its partners, please see (<https://ednaquaplan.com/>).

No personal data is automatically collected in this survey, unless you provide it. Any personal data collected is processed by Seascope Belgium as part of the Horizon Europe project eDNAqua-Plan. This processing is based on your consent (Article 6.1.a of the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR). The data will be accessed only by the project partners and used solely for the purposes outlined above. All published results will be anonymised. It will be retained for 1 year before being deleted.

You have the right to withdraw your consent regarding your personal data. You may exercise these rights by contacting: privacy@seascopebelgium.be

** I confirm that I have read this information and agree to the processing of my data as described above*

- Yes
- No

** I would like to be kept informed of the outputs and events of the eDNAqua-Plan project*

- Yes
- No

Name

Name of the project/ organisation/ initiative that you are involved with

Acronym of the project/ organisation/ initiative

Website of your project/ organisation/ initiative

* In what country are you/ your project/ organisation/ initiative located?

* What category best describes your work/ project/ organisation/ initiative?

- Data generator
- Data repository
- Data user
- Data publisher
- Scientific network
- Policy-funding
- Other

* What is the region of action for your work/ project/ organisation/ initiative?

- Worldwide
- Africa
- Northern Africa
- Sub-Saharan Africa
- Americas
- Latin America & the Caribbean
- Northern America
- Antarctica
- Asia
- Central Asia
- Eastern Asia
- South-eastern Asia
- Southern Asia
- Western Asia
- Europe
- Oceania

* What eDNA-related component best describes your work/ project/ organisation/ initiative?

- Genetic laboratory
- Biodiversity data publishers
- DNA data publishers
- Bioinformatics
- Taxonomic systems & backbones
- Reference libraries
- Biobanks / Culture collections
- Other

* What steps of the eDNA data collection and submission processes are you involved in?

- Sampling
- Laboratory procedures
- Raw sequence data
- Bioinformatics analysis
- Processed sequence data
- Taxonomic assignment
- eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases
- Taxonomic backbone
- Biobanks data - Infrastructure/services

Feedback on eDNAqua-Plan recommendations

Under each section you will find our proposed actions and recommendations each with the same set of three questions, except for the section on 'taxonomic assignment and reference libraries' where there is focused on the essential metadata and the system's architecture. There is extra space provided to elaborate your answer or give additional feedback. You can move back and forth the different sections, the submit button is located at the end of the last page.

Thank you!

General

This section contains general recommendations and actions that are relevant to several parts of the eDNA digital landscape.

Estimated duration: 6 min

1 Publish in specialised repositories (e.g. INSDC repositories) rather than using generalist ones

1.1 Do you agree with this action?

1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please elaborate your previous answer

1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

2 Improve dataset citation and crediting e.g. by implementing a peer review process for data publications (similar to those of scientific journals)

2.1 Do you agree with this action?

2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented

- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

3 Publish metadata using RDF, LOD, and web-tech to ensure submissions are findable and accessible

3.1 Do you agree with this action?

3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

4 Provide training in sampling, in particular related to metadata for fieldwork and experiments and for subsequent processing

4.1 Do you agree with this action?

4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

5 Create a central registry for tools, such as best practices, interoperable (meta)data tools, check lists, guidelines and training

5.1 Do you agree with this action?

5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented

- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

6 Creation of a 'one stop shop' tool that would direct the submitted data and metadata straight to the appropriate repositories

6.1 Do you agree with this action?

6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
 Yes, this has been implemented
 Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

A) Sampling

There is a clear need for stricter and better provision of provenance metadata. Sufficient sampling metadata should always be collected and reported in a standardised manner.

Estimated duration: 5 min

Proposed actions for data repositories (DNA sequence and biodiversity data repositories):

A.1 Make the submission of sample metadata in appropriate repositories (e.g. biosamples) mandatory and link to them

A.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

A.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

A.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Proposed actions for sample metadata repositories:

A.2 Require more mandatory sample metadata fields to ensure more FAIR eDNA data (adopting standards under development e.g. ISO-EN 17805 Sampling, capture and preservation of environmental DNA from water)

A.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

A.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

A.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

A.3 Ensure interoperable metadata by adopting standardised checklists and FAIR vocabularies e.g. for geographical locations (GAZ), habitats (ENVO); ISO standardised terminology (Online browsing platform, ODB or laboratory machinery (OBI))

A.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

A.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

A.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

A.4 Implement integration of sample metadata collected with smartphone apps already used for sample collection (e.g. NMDC Field Notes mobile app, PlutoF GO app)

A.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

A.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

A.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

A.5 Mandatory minimal sample metadata fields (latitude, longitude, depth, associated permits..) would help with traceability and compliance to access and benefit-sharing frameworks, e.g., in the context of the Nagoya Protocol and the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement

A.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

A.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

A.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

B) Laboratory procedures

Sufficient laboratory processing metadata should always be collected and reported in a standardised manner. Ideally the collection of such metadata is a byproduct of the application of laboratory method standards.

Estimated duration: 2 min

Proposed actions for data generators:

B.1 Make use of Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) to generate required metadata in a standardised way

B.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

B.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

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	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

B.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

B.2 Ensure standardised published (ideally open access) protocols are applied or individual protocols are deposited into an appropriate, open resource repository and referenced within the metadata accompanying the raw sequence data

B.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

B.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

B.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future

- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

C) Raw sequence data

Raw sequence data should always be deposited into an open access DNA sequence data repository, ideally an INSDC (NCBI, ENA or DDBJ) repository.

Estimated duration: 4 min

Proposed actions for data generators:

C.1 Always publish data, ideally with an open access licence with data downloadable immediately via that repository/portal (rather than “on demand” from the data generator)

C.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

C.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

C.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Proposed actions for DNA sequence data repositories:

C.2 Expand the number of mandatory metadata fields, focusing on what is needed for FAIR data

C.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

C.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

C.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

C.3 Ensure that metadata are always open, even when data are not

C.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

C.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible

Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

C.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

C.4 Enforce that the content of the metadata is interoperable (e.g. by using controlled vocabularies, using URLs/DOIs in place of IDs or strings)

C.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

C.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

C.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

D) Bioinformatics analysis

Raw sequencing data need to be heavily processed before further analysis can be performed, with methods varying with the used sequencing technology (e.g., PacBio/ONT vs. Illumina/MGI). Bioinformatics analysis can use either automated tools or custom pipelines, but all pipelines should include descriptive metadata (author, version, software, algorithms, etc., such as a CodeMeta file). Outputs must also include provenance metadata, detailing the pipeline used, input parameters, processing agent, date, and sequence identifiers (preferably as URIs).

Estimated duration: 6 min

Proposed actions for data generators:

D.1 Submit the bioinformatics workflows, and the underlying program versions and options in a suitable repository (e.g. Github/Zenodo, workflowhub, etc.) to ensure reproducibility and reusability

D.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

D.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

D.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

D.2 Define and keep intermediary files, with FAIR naming conventions (e.g. those included in the FAIR checklist project)

D.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

D.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

D.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

D.3 Bioinformatics pipelines should be accompanied with descriptive metadata that include various details about the pipeline: the agents (author, maintainer, contact), licence, dates/version, URIs for download/access, software types, included algorithms and reference libraries, etc. (e.g. a CodeMeta file)

D.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

D.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

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	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

D.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

D.4 Bioinformatic processing outputs should be accommodated with provenance metadata on the used pipeline, input parameters, processor, time, and sequences

D.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

D.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

D.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented

- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Proposed actions for biodiversity data repositories and/ or processed sequence data publishers:

D.5 Include or link to bioinformatics metadata into the processed eDNA data in a standardised format (e.g. those defined in the FAIR checklist project)

D.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

D.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

D.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

D.6 Make it mandatory to include essential fields that will allow the interpretation and reuse of the data. E.g. PCR primer information (sequences), coordinates, data contributors/creators/owners, related publications/datasets clustering or error-filtering parameters, and taxonomic identification confidence levels

D.6.1 Do you agree with this action?

D.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

D.6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

E) Processed sequence data

Processed sequencing data is the result of bioinformatics steps like quality filtering, read merging, denoising, and taxonomic assignment. The final output is typically a table of ASVs/OTUs with their read abundances and assigned taxonomies. Few processed datasets are currently shared in accessible, interoperable databases. To ensure trust and reusability, published data should include comprehensive metadata covering sampling, lab procedures, bioinformatics processing, taxonomic assignment, and manual curation. Both the pipeline and its outputs must be documented with metadata, including links to the original sequences.

Estimated duration: 6 min

Proposed actions for journals/ publishers of eDNA research:

E.1 Enforce that eDNA data in publications (e.g. in scientific journals) is published in FAIR repositories and has an accession or other ID, DOI, URI

E.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

E.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

E.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Proposed actions for biodiversity data repositories and/ or processed sequence data publishers:

E.2 Improve data integration from national and institutional databases into global databases

E.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

E.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

E.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

E.3 Ensure that processed eDNA biodiversity data includes the sequences of each (taxonomically assigned) ASV/OTU as well as the persistent identifier linking to the raw sequence data

E.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

E.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

E.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

E.4 Ensure sufficient metadata is provided describing the main processing steps

E.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

E.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

E.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

E.5 Processed eDNA data should always reference the original sequence data, and databases need to ensure correct versioning in case of re-processing of the source data which could lead to different taxonomic interpretations of the original sequence data and inflate biodiversity records

E.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

E.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
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Please explain your previous answer

E.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

E.6 Databases holding original sequence data should be able to track reprocessing of this original data and link to the (potentially different) resulting processed datasets

E.6.1 Do you agree with this action?

E.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

E.6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

F) Taxonomic assignment and reference libraries

Estimated duration: 20 min

F.I) Vision for the future of reference libraries in three parts

eDNAqua-Plan's vision aims to maintain independently curated reference libraries, but ensure that they follow common, guiding curation principles and metadata requirements, enabling them to be interconnected and easily discoverable.

This vision relies on three main pillars:

1) Reference libraries are curated, for sequence quality as well as taxonomic reliability. All primary sequence data are deposited in or harvested from primary nucleotide repositories (ENA, GenBank, BOLD). The quality control and taxonomic curation of these sequences then follows a set of guiding principles, where the goal of the taxonomic curation is to homogenise taxonomic names for a given phylogenetic clade (or for identical/ near-identical sequences).

2) All reference libraries adhere to a set of minimal but essential metadata accompanying the reference sequence data. This restricted set of fields allow end-users to easily identify whether the taxonomic assignment linked to a barcode is trustworthy, and be able to filter database entries according to a set of pertinent criteria (geographic location, habitat type, environmental parameters, etc.).

3) Reference libraries are connected in a federated system, which relies on common data formats, interoperable metadata fields, and a decentralised data architecture. This data architecture must ensure a federated network allowing for each reference library to maintain their independence, while still making the data easy to find and query.

Do you agree with this vision, focusing on maintaining the independence of individual, curated reference libraries but connecting them in a federated network?

Why yes, or why not? Are there other essential aspects?

F.II) Proposal for a set of essential metadata

A reference barcode must be accompanied by a minimum set of metadata. Here, the DNA sequence is considered as primary data and all accompanying information as metadata. Having the appropriate metadata accompanying a reference sequence allows verification of the identification of the sequence, which is crucial to curate taxonomic assignments and ensure the quality/ reliability of downstream results.

The eDNAqua-Plan recommendation for the minimum set of essential metadata for reference libraries focuses on a relatively restricted set of fields that allow end-users to:

- (1) easily identify whether the taxonomic assignment linked to a barcode is trustworthy
- (2) be able to filter database entries according to a set of pertinent criteria (geographic location, habitat type, environmental parameters, etc.).

Below we invite you to agree or disagree with the inclusion of each field in this restricted set of essential metadata, vote for each field to be mandatory or recommended, and add any further comments.

Category	Field	Description	Agree/ Disagree	Mandatory/ Recommended	Comments
Biological Origin	Source material identifier	Unique code to identify the specimen, culture, or (environmental) sample from which the reference sequence is originally obtained	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Repository	Name of museum, biobank, culture collection from which specimen originates	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Sample type	Whether the barcode originates from an individual specimen, a culture, or an environmental sequencing dataset	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Date of collection	Preferably in ISO-format (YYYY-MM-DD)	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Geographic origin	Latitude/ longitude (e.g., expressed in decimal values in WGS84 or in a different, specified geographical positioning system), locality, country, water body for marine samples	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Habitat/ environment type	E.g., pelagic, benthic, soil, host-associated - need defined list?)	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Habitat/ environment type	In metres	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Depth/ elevation	In metres	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Temperature and/ or salinity (when relevant)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Sample permits? (e.g. ABS)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Specimen identification	Taxonomic name linked to specimen by person who originally identified it	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Original identification method	Morphological, molecular, or both	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Biological Origin	Type material	Is the specimen/ culture used to generate the barcode the same specimen/ culture designated as type material of the species	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	

Biological Origin	Image(s) of voucher specimen/ or link to images in external database		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Sequence accession number		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Source database name	GenBank, ENA, BOLD, PR2, etc.	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Source database version		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Marker/ gene region	e.g., 18S, COI, rbcL, ITS	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Sequence length		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Sequencing platform (e.g., Sanger, Illumina, Nanopore)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Sequencing instrument		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Quality metrics (e.g., % ambiguous bases, Phred score - need defined list?)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Quality control notes (e.g., chimera check, contamination screening, trimming notes)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Consensus sequence method	Method or pipeline used to obtain the consensus sequence from environmental samples	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	Link to associated publication or project		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Sequence information	BLAST nearest match		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Curation status	Raw/ expert-reviewed	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	

Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Curator/ expert validator name (+ institute/ country/ contact details)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Date of expert validation		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Confidence level method (defined list?)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Confidence level score/ rank		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Curation method	Phylogeny, cluster, etc. - need defined list?)	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Taxonomic name	Current valid name according to an accepted taxonomy - the most reliable identification to the lowest possible taxonomic rank	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Taxonomic source	Name of taxonomic database (e.g., WoRMS, AlgaeBase, NCBI Taxonomy, SILVA)	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Taxonomic identifier	Identifier in taxonomic database corresponding to the scientific name	<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Taxonomy and taxonomic validation	Synonyms/ previous names		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Library metadata	Library name		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Library metadata	Library version number		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Library metadata	Library version data		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	
Library metadata	Cross-links to other reference systems (e.g., GBIF, OBIS, WoRMS)		<input type="radio"/> Agree <input type="radio"/> Disagree	<input type="radio"/> Mandatory <input type="radio"/> Recommended	

Are there any fields that are missing from this list, but you consider would be essential to include in a restricted set? If yes, please give them below with a short description and explanation for their inclusion.

F.III) Potential data architecture behind the federated system

There are different possibilities to make the federated system happen in a sustainable and pragmatic fashion. Here, we consider two solutions to the data architecture behind a federated system of curated reference libraries.

1) Independent libraries, fully decentralised, common formats, and a common (meta)data search tool or crawler.

In this structure, reference libraries are individually managed and maintained on separate servers. They ensure that their data is available in an agreed-upon format, following the proposed metadata and data standard, and accessible through an API. A data or metadata search portal or engine would then allow querying the curated reference libraries that adhere to the common format to make their data findable across libraries.

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer, are there any barriers or levers that you think of?

2) Independent libraries, periodic data exports in common formats to a centralised repository.

In this structure, reference libraries are individually managed and maintained on separate servers. However, they release data exports in an agreed-upon format, following the proposed metadata and data standard, in a central repository. This central repository centralises the versioned copies of separate databases in one location, and allows easy access from the different sources.

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer, are there any barriers or levers that you think of?

Which of the two architectures would you rather see implemented?

- Independent and decentralised with a common search engine
- Independent with regular, centralised data exports

F.IV) Recommendations

Proposed actions for reference library providers:

F.1 Recommend, define and implement essential metadata and common taxonomic curation principles, anchored in international methodological and laboratory standards, that enable quality-control and curation (and thus establish the reliability of the taxonomic assignment later on)

F.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

F.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

F.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

F.2 Create a recognition system for databases/ libraries that follow the essential metadata recommendations and curation requirements through a certification process and quality label at EU-level. This could aid in procuring long-term funding for recognised reference libraries and encourage their use

F.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

F.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

F.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

F.3 Establish connections between recognised/ curated reference databases so they can communicate through an integrated network. This should be achieved by implementing interoperability through common metadata standard vocabularies (e.g. MixS vocabulary) and communicating through a data exchange protocol (e.g. borrowing ideas from HUPO-PSI), ideally using RDF, LOD, and web-technologies (e.g. JSON-LD)

F.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

F.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

F.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

F.4 Establish a feedback system from curators and users back to the data generators in primary databases, e.g. through the additions of annotations to ENA objects as done by UNITE using the Contextual Data Clearing House (CDCH)

F.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

F.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

F.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Proposed actions for funding agencies:

F.5 Create long-term funding streams for reference libraries with the proposed EU-level certification and quality label, identifying them as a resource of strategic importance

F.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

F.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible

Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

F.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G) eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases

The largest global players are GBIF and OBIS, fed by their various nodes and data providers. The data standard used is DwC-A, with the DNA-extension to DwC-A being used to accommodate DNA-specific information. The metadata standard – the vocabulary used in the CSV files that make up the DwC dataset – is DwC, and this links to the MIxS standard for the omics-specific terms. This extension is currently not a standard as defined and maintained by TDWG, but it is the standard used by GBIF, OBIS and EurOBIS.

Estimated duration: 8 min

Proposed actions for data generators:

G.1 Publish all eDNA-based occurrences as biodiversity data, and not only in scientific publications (or not at all). This applies even where no scientific paper is produced from a project

G.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible

Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Proposed actions for biodiversity data repositories:

G.2 Better collaboration between various national, global and thematic biodiversity data publishers in adopting common data and metadata standards and schemata

G.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented

- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G.3 Better collaboration between global biodiversity data published (in particular GBIF and OBIS) and leading DNA data publishers (including GSC and INSDC), to align on standards, particularly in the use of vocabularies and the definitions and mandatory nature of terms

G.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G.4 Improve interoperability of submitted (meta)data, requiring use of URIs or even better PURLs rather than strings, allowing machines to reliably use values

G.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G.5 Implement a certification and quality labelling process to recognise eDNA based occurrences with sufficient and quality-controlled (meta)data (eDNAquaplan could provide a set of essential metadata terms agreed upon by the wider community, and operational (meta)data standards)

G.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G.6 Include provenance templates when describing data originating from biological (and in our case, eDNA) material. Such templates should be created, e.g. via community collaboration

G.6.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G.7 Enforce the mapping of omics and the traditional taxonomic naming systems to have more discoverable and understandable eDNA results for the biodiversity data user

G.7.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.7.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.7.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

G.8 Support interoperable and open data originating from bioinformatics pipelines, which then can allow more generalised tools to be created to convert those to whatever format and schema the biodiversity data publishers require (which at present is DwC-A and the DwC vocabulary)

G.8.1 Do you agree with this action?

G.8.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

G.8.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

H) Taxonomic backbone

Estimated duration: 1 min

H.1 Improve collaboration and mapping of omics and traditional taxonomic naming systems so that eDNA results are more discoverable and understandable by biodiversity data users and that changes can be dealt with efficiently and in a scientific correct way

H.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

H.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

H.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

I) Biobanks' data infrastructures/ services

The rapid loss of aquatic biodiversity is increasing the important role that biobanks play in preserving genetic diversity and resources. While successfully preserving a broad spectrum of biological materials and consistently connecting physical specimens and their genetic information through structured metadata systems, there is a need for more sharing of information, consistent data standards and taxonomic referencing, better sample traceability and bioinformatics integration, better DNA management practices, reliable backup systems and sufficiently represented species.

Estimated duration: 3 min

Proposed actions for biobanks/culture collection:

1.1 Improve workflow tracking (e.g. Laboratory Information Management Systems LIMS) and move towards accessible digital databases (away from Excel)

I.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

I.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

I.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

I.2 Collaborate to adopt standards to allow for increased interoperability and harmonisation, in particular taxonomic and DNA-specific metadata standards and by providing more detailed metadata about advanced genomic and bioinformatic workflows

I.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

I.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible
Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

I.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

I.3 Implement a quality label when complying with appropriate good practice and standards

I.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

I.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective?

	Not feasible	Partially feasible, significant challenges exist	Fully feasible

Technical	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Policy/ Strategic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Resources (time/ budget)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please explain your previous answer

I.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

- No, not in the foreseeable future
- Yes, this has been implemented
- Yes, in the near future

Challenges or other feedback?

Useful links

[Zenodo eDNAqua-Plan \(https://zenodo.org/communities/ednaquaplan/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest\)](https://zenodo.org/communities/ednaquaplan/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)

[Website eDNAqua-Plan \(https://ednaquaplan.com/\)](https://ednaquaplan.com/)

Background Documents

[eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7: The eDNAqua-Plan conceptual landscape proposal](#)

Contact

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Table 2. Generated Statistics from EUSurvey tool

Statistics: eDNAqua-Plan: Stakeholder Consultation Survey

I confirm that I have read this information and agree to the processing of my data as described above

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		23	100 %
No		0	0 %
No Answer		0	0 %

I would like to be kept informed of the outputs and events of the eDNAqua-Plan project

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		22	95.65 %
No		1	4.35 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What category best describes your work/ project/ organisation/ initiative?

		Answers	Ratio
Data generator		16	69.57 %
Data repository		1	4.35 %
Data user		11	47.83 %
Data publisher		12	52.17 %
Scientific network		9	39.13 %
Policy-funding		2	8.7 %
Other		1	4.35 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What is the region of action for your work/ project/ organisation/ initiative?

		Answers	Ratio
Worldwide		6	26.09 %
Africa		1	4.35 %
Northern Africa		0	0 %
Sub-Saharan Africa		0	0 %
Americas		0	0 %
Latin America & the Caribbean		1	4.35 %
Northern America		0	0 %
Antarctica		0	0 %
Asia		0	0 %
Central Asia		0	0 %
Eastern Asia		0	0 %
South-eastern Asia		0	0 %
Southern Asia		0	0 %
Western Asia		0	0 %
Europe		13	56.52 %
Oceania		3	13.04 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What eDNA-related component best describes your work/ project/ organisation/ initiative?

		Answers	Ratio
Genetic laboratory		15	65.22 %
Biodiversity data publishers		11	47.83 %
DNA data publishers		12	52.17 %
Bioinformatics		10	43.48 %
Taxonomic systems & backbones		5	21.74 %
Reference libraries		10	43.48 %
Biobanks / Culture collections		3	13.04 %
Other		1	4.35 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What steps of the eDNA data collection and submission processes are you involved in?

		Answers	Ratio
Sampling		20	86.96 %
Laboratory procedures		18	78.26 %
Raw sequence data		14	60.87 %
Bioinformatics analysis		16	69.57 %
Processed sequence data		16	69.57 %
Taxonomic assignment		18	78.26 %
eDNA occurrences in biodiversity databases		17	73.91 %
Taxonomic backbone		5	21.74 %
Biobanks data - Infrastructure/services		3	13.04 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
1		1	4.35 %
2		5	21.74 %
3		7	30.43 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		13	56.52 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		11	47.83 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		15	65.22 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		12	52.17 %
Yes, this has been implemented		2	8.7 %
Yes, in the near future		8	34.78 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		3	13.04 %
2		6	26.09 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		9	39.13 %
No Answer		0	0 %

 1 2 3 4

2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		17	73.91 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		4	17.39 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		15	65.22 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		16	69.57 %
Yes, this has been implemented		3	13.04 %
Yes, in the near future		3	13.04 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		2	8.7 %
2		5	21.74 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		11	47.83 %
No Answer		0	0 %

3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		14	60.87 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		16	69.57 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		10	43.48 %
Yes, this has been implemented		5	21.74 %
Yes, in the near future		5	21.74 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		0	0 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		17	73.91 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		15	65.22 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		15	65.22 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		16	69.57 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		4	17.39 %
Yes, in the near future		10	43.48 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

5.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		17	73.91 %
No Answer		0	0 %

5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		0	0 %

5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		0	0 %

5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		16	69.57 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		0	0 %

5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		14	60.87 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		7	30.43 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

6.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		8	34.78 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		0	0 %

6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		14	60.87 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		16	69.57 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		17	73.91 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		5	21.74 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		6	26.09 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		4	17.39 %
Fully feasible		17	73.91 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		13	56.52 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		9	39.13 %
Yes, in the near future		5	21.74 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		7	30.43 %
4		11	47.83 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		16	69.57 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		8	34.78 %
Yes, this has been implemented		5	21.74 %
Yes, in the near future		8	34.78 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		14	60.87 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		15	65.22 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		13	56.52 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

A.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		9	39.13 %
Yes, this has been implemented		5	21.74 %
Yes, in the near future		6	26.09 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		1	4.35 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		5	21.74 %
3		10	43.48 %
4		5	21.74 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		13	56.52 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

A.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		14	60.87 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

A.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		2	8.7 %
Fully feasible		17	73.91 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		4	17.39 %
Fully feasible		15	65.22 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

A.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		13	56.52 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

A.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		2	8.7 %
Yes, this has been implemented		9	39.13 %
Yes, in the near future		6	26.09 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

B.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		1	4.35 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		5	21.74 %
3		6	26.09 %
4		8	34.78 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

B.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		14	60.87 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

B.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

B.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

B.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		11	47.83 %
Yes, this has been implemented		4	17.39 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

B.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		3	13.04 %
4		16	69.57 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

B.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

B.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

B.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

B.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		3	13.04 %
Yes, in the near future		7	30.43 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

C.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

C.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

C.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

C.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

C.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		8	34.78 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		1	4.35 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

C.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		4	17.39 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

C.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		8	34.78 %
4		9	39.13 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

C.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		3	13.04 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		5	21.74 %
Yes, in the near future		3	13.04 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

C.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		3	13.04 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

C.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

C.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		3	13.04 %
Yes, this has been implemented		2	8.7 %
Yes, in the near future		8	34.78 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

D.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		13	56.52 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

D.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		12	52.17 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		6	26.09 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

D.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		3	13.04 %
2		8	34.78 %
3		2	8.7 %
4		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

D.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

D.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		1	4.35 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

D.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		12	52.17 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

D.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		1	4.35 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		6	26.09 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

D.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

D.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

D.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

D.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		3	13.04 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

D.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		1	4.35 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

D.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		5	21.74 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

D.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

D.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

D.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		5	21.74 %
Yes, this has been implemented		5	21.74 %
Yes, in the near future		3	13.04 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

D.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		6	26.09 %
4		11	47.83 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

D.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

D.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

D.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		2	8.7 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

D.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		11	47.83 %

D.6.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		15	65.22 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

D.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		11	47.83 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

D.6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		5	21.74 %
Yes, this has been implemented		6	26.09 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

E.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		2	8.7 %
2		0	0 %
3		2	8.7 %
4		18	78.26 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

E.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		11	47.83 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

E.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		11	47.83 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

E.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

E.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		6	26.09 %
Yes, in the near future		3	13.04 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

E.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		2	8.7 %
4		16	69.57 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

E.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

E.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

E.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

E.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		4	17.39 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		8	34.78 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

E.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		14	60.87 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

E.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

E.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

E.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

E.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		9	39.13 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

E.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		2	8.7 %
4		19	82.61 %
No Answer		1	4.35 %

E.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

E.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		11	47.83 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

E.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

E.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		3	13.04 %
Yes, this has been implemented		4	17.39 %
Yes, in the near future		7	30.43 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

E.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		0	0 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		16	69.57 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

E.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

E.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

E.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

E.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		3	13.04 %
Yes, in the near future		3	13.04 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

E.6.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		2	8.7 %
2		4	17.39 %
3		2	8.7 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

E.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

E.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

E.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		2	8.7 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

E.6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		9	39.13 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

Do you agree with this vision, focusing on maintaining the independence of individual, curated reference libraries but connecting them in a federated network?

		Answers	Ratio
0		13	56.52 %
1		4	17.39 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		18	78.26 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		13	56.52 %
Recommended		6	26.09 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		10	43.48 %
Recommended		8	34.78 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		18	78.26 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		16	69.57 %
Recommended		1	4.35 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		16	69.57 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		14	60.87 %
Recommended		5	21.74 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		16	69.57 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		16	69.57 %
Recommended		3	13.04 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		11	47.83 %
Recommended		7	30.43 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		13	56.52 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		4	17.39 %
Recommended		9	39.13 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		6	26.09 %
Recommended		12	52.17 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		14	60.87 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		5	21.74 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		14	60.87 %
Disagree		4	17.39 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		5	21.74 %
Recommended		12	52.17 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		9	39.13 %
Recommended		10	43.48 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		11	47.83 %
Recommended		6	26.09 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		15	65.22 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		9	39.13 %
Recommended		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Biological Origin : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		15	65.22 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Biological Origin : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		2	8.7 %
Recommended		15	65.22 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		18	78.26 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		16	69.57 %
Recommended		2	8.7 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		14	60.87 %
Recommended		3	13.04 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		12	52.17 %
Disagree		4	17.39 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		5	21.74 %
Recommended		8	34.78 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		18	78.26 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		19	82.61 %
Recommended		0	0 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		18	78.26 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		10	43.48 %
Recommended		9	39.13 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		18	78.26 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		11	47.83 %
Recommended		8	34.78 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		14	60.87 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		4	17.39 %
Recommended		12	52.17 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		4	17.39 %
Recommended		15	65.22 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		14	60.87 %
Disagree		2	8.7 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		6	26.09 %
Recommended		10	43.48 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		9	39.13 %
Recommended		9	39.13 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		16	69.57 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		4	17.39 %
Recommended		13	56.52 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Sequence information : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		11	47.83 %
Disagree		4	17.39 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

- : Sequence information : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		2	8.7 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		15	65.22 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		6	26.09 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		14	60.87 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		1	4.35 %
Recommended		16	69.57 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		9	39.13 %
Disagree		6	26.09 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		1	4.35 %
Recommended		13	56.52 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		12	52.17 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		4	17.39 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		11	47.83 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		3	13.04 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		14	60.87 %
Disagree		2	8.7 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		2	8.7 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		17	73.91 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		11	47.83 %
Recommended		7	30.43 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		16	69.57 %
Disagree		0	0 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		12	52.17 %
Recommended		6	26.09 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		13	56.52 %
Disagree		2	8.7 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		8	34.78 %
Recommended		8	34.78 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		8	34.78 %
Disagree		8	34.78 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

- : Taxonomy and taxonomic validation : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		0	0 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		12	52.17 %

- : Library metadata : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		12	52.17 %
Disagree		1	4.35 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Library metadata : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		7	30.43 %
Recommended		6	26.09 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Library metadata : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		10	43.48 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

- : Library metadata : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		5	21.74 %
Recommended		6	26.09 %
No Answer		12	52.17 %

- : Library metadata : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		9	39.13 %
Disagree		3	13.04 %
No Answer		11	47.83 %

- : Library metadata : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		4	17.39 %
Recommended		6	26.09 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %

- : Library metadata : Agree/ Disagree

		Answers	Ratio
Agree		13	56.52 %
Disagree		4	17.39 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

- : Library metadata : Mandatory/ Recommended

		Answers	Ratio
Mandatory		2	8.7 %
Recommended		11	47.83 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		14	60.87 %
Fully feasible		2	8.7 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		14	60.87 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

Which of the two architectures would you rather see implemented?

		Answers	Ratio
Independent and decentralised with a common search engine		11	47.83 %
Independent with regular, centralised data exports		7	30.43 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

F.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		0	0 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		14	60.87 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

F.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

F.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

F.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

F.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		8	34.78 %
Yes, this has been implemented		2	8.7 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		11	47.83 %

F.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

F.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

F.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

F.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

F.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		10	43.48 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		3	13.04 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

F.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		3	13.04 %
4		11	47.83 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

F.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		15	65.22 %
Fully feasible		1	4.35 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

F.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

F.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		15	65.22 %
Fully feasible		0	0 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

F.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		9	39.13 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

F.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		6	26.09 %
4		7	30.43 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

F.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

F.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

F.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		4	17.39 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		0	0 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

F.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		9	39.13 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		1	4.35 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %

F.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		2	8.7 %
4		16	69.57 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

F.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

F.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

F.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

F.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		10	43.48 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		1	4.35 %
No Answer		12	52.17 %

G.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		3	13.04 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		6	26.09 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

G.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		3	13.04 %
Yes, in the near future		6	26.09 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

G.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		0	0 %
3		3	13.04 %
4		17	73.91 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

G.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		7	30.43 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

G.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		0	0 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		15	65.22 %
No Answer		3	13.04 %

G.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		5	21.74 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		5	21.74 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %

G.4.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		4	17.39 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		9	39.13 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

G.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		4	17.39 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

G.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

G.4.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		11	47.83 %

G.4.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %

G.5.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		9	39.13 %
4		6	26.09 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.5.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

G.5.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		10	43.48 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		11	47.83 %

G.6.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		1	4.35 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		5	21.74 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		2	8.7 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.6.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		13	56.52 %
Fully feasible		2	8.7 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

G.6.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		1	4.35 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		14	60.87 %

G.7.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		6	26.09 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		7	30.43 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

G.7.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

G.7.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		3	13.04 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

G.7.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		11	47.83 %
Fully feasible		2	8.7 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

G.7.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %

G.8.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

G.8.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		6	26.09 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

G.8.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

G.8.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

G.8.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		1	4.35 %
No Answer		15	65.22 %

H.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		4	17.39 %
4		16	69.57 %
No Answer		2	8.7 %

H.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

H.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

H.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		12	52.17 %
Fully feasible		3	13.04 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

H.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		7	30.43 %
Yes, this has been implemented		2	8.7 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		10	43.48 %

I.1.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		3	13.04 %
3		7	30.43 %
4		8	34.78 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

I.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		10	43.48 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		6	26.09 %

I.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

I.1.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		16	69.57 %
Fully feasible		0	0 %
No Answer		7	30.43 %

I.1.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		4	17.39 %
Yes, this has been implemented		5	21.74 %
Yes, in the near future		2	8.7 %
No Answer		12	52.17 %

I.2.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		1	4.35 %
3		5	21.74 %
4		12	52.17 %
No Answer		5	21.74 %

I.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		8	34.78 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

I.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		7	30.43 %
Fully feasible		7	30.43 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

I.2.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		1	4.35 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		9	39.13 %
Fully feasible		5	21.74 %
No Answer		8	34.78 %

I.2.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		2	8.7 %
Yes, this has been implemented		2	8.7 %
Yes, in the near future		6	26.09 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %

I.3.1 Do you agree with this action?

		Answers	Ratio
0		0	0 %
1		0	0 %
2		2	8.7 %
3		7	30.43 %
4		10	43.48 %
No Answer		4	17.39 %

I.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Technical

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		4	17.39 %
Fully feasible		10	43.48 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

I.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Policy/ Strategic

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		5	21.74 %
Fully feasible		9	39.13 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

I.3.2 What would be the feasibility of this action from a technical, policy/ strategic and resources perspective? : Resources (time/ budget)

		Answers	Ratio
Not feasible		0	0 %
Partially feasible, significant challenges exist		8	34.78 %
Fully feasible		6	26.09 %
No Answer		9	39.13 %

I.3.3 Is this a priority for your organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
No, not in the foreseeable future		6	26.09 %
Yes, this has been implemented		0	0 %
Yes, in the near future		4	17.39 %
No Answer		13	56.52 %